

**THE ISSUE OF GRAMMATICAL DESCRIPTIONS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL
UNITS**

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Annotation: In this article, the practical and scientific-theoretical aspects of the field of phraseological lexicology (phraseography) are studied. Also, in the article, the nature of the phrase, the relationship between form and content in the phrase, the mental characteristics of the problem are analyzed, and serious attention is paid to some issues of Uzbek phraseography, which has formed as an independent field.

Key words: *phraseology, phraseography, mental features, language perfection, grammatical signs, polysemantic features.*

It is known that language as a social phenomenon in motion is regularly updated according to the requirements of the situation. Changes in social life affect language relations in the form of internal and external factors. Taking this into account, our government has developed a system of appropriate measures to improve the language policy. Therefore, by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 311 of September 10, 1996, the task of compiling a multi-volume explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language is included in the state program. Organizational work related to its preparation for publication was entrusted to the Institute of Language and Literature named after FA Alisher Navoi (now the Institute of Uzbek Language, Literature and Folklore). The current situation is the product of certain scientific and practical needs.

Because the existing two-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" (1981) containing 60,000 words and word forms, firstly, did not cover the progress made by practical Uzbek lexicography in recent years, and secondly, the old-fashioned The article cannot fill the gap in the worldview of the new era, thirdly, in each new source that is filled and enriched, the word form changes in meaning. In current studies, it has been revealed on the basis of concrete evidence that the polysemantic feature of idioms is a unique expression of the semantic development of the phraseological system of that language. But in the science of phraseology, there are no different views on the process of the emergence of a polysemous phrase.

It is known that, on the one hand, a phrase is an object of lexicographic analysis from the point of view of codification in different dictionaries, and on the other hand, it is a product of the semantic process that shows different semantic relations of words and possibilities of combination (linking). Accordingly, the issues of lexicographical interpretation of phrases have attracted the attention of scientists for many years. For example, H. Berdiyurov put the creation of phraseological dictionaries in Uzbek on the agenda at the 1st inter-republican scientific conference on phraseological issues held in Samarkand in 1959. According to the scientist, the work of creating a phraseological dictionary in the Uzbek language should be carried out in the following three stages:

The main semasiological law in the development of any language is related to the multi-meaning (polysemantic) nature of those language units. Accordingly, some scientists consider polysemy to be one of the objective indicators of language development [1; 20]. Accordingly, since the 70s of the last century, a number of candidate works on the analysis of phraseological polysemy appeared in linguistics [2; 109].

In such a dictionary, it is necessary to be based on the principle of the alphabet. In it, idioms are given in alphabetical order, and then their use in figurative and figurative meanings is explained; then examples from fiction and local press are given. It is also necessary to provide synonyms, different variants, expressions in live speech and dialects of selected phrases for the dictionary.

Taking into account the need for hundreds of thousands of pupils and students in schools in Uzbekistan to study their mother tongue, as well as the Russian language, Russian-Uzbek and Uzbek-Russian dictionaries with 3-4 thousand phrases have been prepared for them. It is necessary to make at. In this case, the equivalents of phrases in one language in another language are given. It is necessary to start creating a card index of existing phrases in the Uzbek language [3; 70].

It has been a long time since Mushohad was promoted. Currently, about ten types of phraseological dictionary have been created, practical and scientific-theoretical aspects of the field of phraseological lexicology (phraseography) have been studied. In the next stage of research, the nature of the phrase, the relationship between form and content in the phrase, and the mental characteristics of the problem were analyzed. It is noteworthy that serious attention has been paid to some issues of Uzbek phraseography, which has formed as an independent field.

The well-known lexicographer-scientist S. Akobirov was specially engaged in the interpretation of phraseological units in explanatory dictionaries. According to the scientist, phraseological issues in lexicography can be considered in different aspects: 1) In what form

should idioms be presented in the "Dictionary"? 2) How should phrases be placed in the "Dictionary" (given in which component article)? 3) How should a phrasal verb be placed in a dictionary article? 4) In what cases and in what order should phrases be explained in the "Dictionary"? 5) How much evidence (examples and quotations) are necessary to confirm and demonstrate the meanings given to phrases in the explanatory dictionary and their use in these meanings? 6) Grammatical and stylistic description of phrases in the "Dictionary".

It is clear that a mature specialist determines the promising directions of Uzbek phraseology and phraseography. One of the important problems in the interpretation of polysemantic phrases with three or more meanings in dictionaries is related to determining the primary and secondary meanings of the phrase. Such a problem resolves itself if a polysemantic expression is ambiguous, with the primary meaning placed first and the artificial or figurative meaning second. But if a polysemantic phrase has three or more meanings, it becomes a bit more complicated to determine its main or leading meaning. Prof. this problem. Sh. Rakhmatullayev tries to explain as follows: "The meaning of the phrase is based on a certain image, it is embodied in a kind of generalized meaning, therefore the main meaning cannot be called the correct meaning. in a phrase that creates a homonymy relationship with the connection, the main phraseological meaning is in the state of a figurative meaning. can be recognized as meaning".

The linguist-scientist H. Casares explained the polysemy of phrases in his time as the combination of two or more phrases in one speech sign (meaning). It is a very complicated process to distinguish PFs and interpret them lexicographically in dictionaries. Therefore, until now, the meanings of PFs are interpreted very differently in different dictionaries. In this article, the practical and scientific-theoretical aspects of the field of phraseological lexicology (phraseography) are studied. Also, in the article, the nature of the phrase, the relationship between form and content in the phrase, the mental characteristics of the problem are analyzed, and serious attention is paid to some issues of Uzbek phraseography, which has formed as an independent field.

In the phrase, the scope of use of the word and the creative possibility are mutually complementary, determining and connecting components. The relationship between primary and secondary meaning plays a crucial role in it. A ready-made construction in the language centers the nation's worldview and evaluation criteria. Expression and interpretation are combined in a unit that carries the overall and generalized meaning. It combines emotional-expressive coloring, the level of stylistic specificity and the practice of speech skills. The perception of a member of society leads to the semantic renewal of the concept. In the folk phrase "wear your coat upside down", the action nomination was created on the basis of a free combination of words. In it, the

combination of language, speech and culture creates a national mentality. This phrase, which expresses the interest and need of the people to which the person belongs, represents the process of getting angry. The landscape of mental state, the clarity of life experience determines the naturalness of understanding.

"Phraseological units are a multifaceted and multi-layered mental structure that shows the psychological, cognitive-semantic and linguocultural aspects of the people. In their essence, there is a content that is perceived socially or subjectively, reflects the important material, mental, and spiritual aspects of human life, and reflects the life experience of the people with historical roots. In traditional linguistics, language units, including phraseological units, were studied mainly on the basis of their structural features.

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